

Exploring Readiness Gaps in the Pilot Implementation of the Strengthened Senior High School Curriculum in the Philippines

Rico M. Aya-ay , Angelica Kean T. Bantasan, Germin A. Cajes, Jinky H. Cajes
Holy Cross of Davao College, Davao City, Philippines

Abstract

The Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) is adopting the Strengthened Senior High School (SHS) Curriculum in selected schools to address long-standing concerns about curriculum overload, skill mismatch, and learning relevance. Despite its reform-oriented aims, increasing concerns suggest significant gaps in preparedness during early implementation. This study looked at the lived experiences of teachers and school administrators in chosen pilot senior high schools in Davao City, with an emphasis on issues such as organizational readiness, teacher training, and instructional resources. The study took a qualitative phenomenological method based on Thorndike's Law of Readiness, with purposely selected teachers and school administrators actively participating in the curriculum rollout. A semi-structured in-depth interviews discussions were utilized to collect data, which was then thematically analyzed. The findings revealed two major themes: (1) Experiencing Challenges in Curriculum Implementation, and (2) Demonstrating Teacher Adaptability and Professional Growth. According to the study, successful curriculum reform requires a mix of teacher readiness and institutional competency. To guarantee successful and fair curriculum implementation, proposals include increased pre-implementation planning, continued professional development, timely delivery of instructional resources, improved school infrastructure, and the formation of professional learning communities.

Keywords: *Senior High School, Department of Education, Strengthen Senior High School Curriculum, School Systems in the Philippines.*

Suggested citation: Aya-ay, R.M., Bantasan, A.K.T., Cajes, G.A., & Cajes, J.H. (2026). Exploring Readiness Gaps in the Pilot Implementation of the Strengthened Senior High School Curriculum in the Philippines. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 208-219. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2026.3(3).20

Introduction

The Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) is testing a "Strengthened Senior High School (SHS) Curriculum" during the 2025-2026 school year. The revision aims to address long-standing issues about curriculum overload, inadequate alignment with employment expectations, and insufficient resource help. However, preliminary data indicate a troubling trend: the pilot looks to suffer from substantial flaws in planning, teacher training, and teaching materials, all of which pose significant impediments to effective implementation.

Curriculum changes fail on a frequent basis across the world owing to a lack of preparation, inadequate teacher training, and insufficient resources, as witnessed in Sub-Saharan Africa (UNESCO, 2022). In the Philippines, the K-12 and continuing Strengthened SHS Curriculum implementation has been impeded by late curriculum guides, hasty training, and a paucity of materials, leaving educators unprepared (Orbeta et al., 2019; Helpline PH, 2025). Local officials in Davao City, where the program is still deemed

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

experimental, cite teacher reluctance, insufficient training, and material shortages as barriers to implementation (Bentayao et al, 2024).

Despite the purpose of increasing learning outcomes through the Strengthened SHS Curriculum, little attention has been given to the actual implementation process. Schools were given inadequate time to prepare, with curriculum guides arriving late and instructors receiving just one-time, quick training sessions rather than ongoing professional development. Furthermore, due to limited resources and instructor reluctance, the program has been classified as "experimental," with unknown outcomes. This gap emphasizes the crucial need to investigate how short planning time, insufficient training, and financial restrictions hinder curriculum implementation integrity in pilot schools.

This is based on Edward Thorndike's Law of Readiness (1913), which asserts that individuals learn and perform best when they are intellectually, professionally, and financially prepared. Inadequate preparation leads to uncomfortable and ineffective performance. In the context of curriculum reform, this theory highlights the importance of teachers' motivation, preparedness, and the availability of supporting environments. The framework guides the interpretation of teachers' lived experiences by looking at how their sense of preparedness (or lack thereof) influences their ability to deliver the curriculum successfully. It also adds to the study's phenomenological emphasis on comprehending the link between professional devotion, systemic support, and the contextual realities of reform implementation.

Materials And Methods

This study uses a qualitative phenomenological design to investigate and characterize the core of participants lived experiences in relation to a specific phenomenon (Moustakas, 1994). The situation in question is the occurrence of preparedness gaps during the trial implementation of the Strengthened SHS Curriculum. This approach enables for a thorough knowledge of how teachers and school leaders perceive, interpret, and make sense of their experiences during the reform process. The study was carried out in selected public and private senior high schools in Davao City, which was recognized as one of the Strengthened SHS Curriculum's pilot sites. Davao City has a diversified educational environment that includes both urban and semi-rural contexts, allowing for the investigation of various levels of preparedness and resource availability.

Participants include teachers and school officials (principals, department heads, and pilot program coordinators) who are directly involved in the implementation of the Strengthened SHS Curriculum. The purposive sampling strategy is used to choose individuals who have personal experience with the pilot deployment. Approximately 6 to 8 participants are desired to ensure a balanced representation of opinions from various schools and topic areas. The quantity is judged sufficient for data saturation, which occurs when no new insights emerge despite continuing data collecting.

The data gathering procedure begins with obtaining the requisite clearance from the School Heads. Once approval was obtained, potential participants were approached individually and given an informed consent form outlining the study's aim, confidentiality protocols, the voluntary nature of their involvement, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Following consent, the researcher conducted semi-structured, in-depth interviews to collect detailed accounts of participants lived experiences throughout the pilot implementation of the Strengthened SHS curriculum. Each interview lasted between 20 and 30 minutes and was audio-recorded with the participants' agreement to verify accuracy. All recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim immediately following the sessions to verify the authenticity of participants' responses and adherence to their original expressions throughout the analytic process.

This study employed a semi-structured questionnaire, which is a sort of survey instrument used to collect information from study participants. It comprises both open-ended and closed-ended questions, with some requiring a precise response and others allowing for more detailed and personalized responses. The interview guide was developed by the researcher. The interview guide included questions designed to

elicit the experiences, coping strategies, and perspectives of public-school teachers serving on the electoral board. Furthermore, probing questions were developed and verified for use in both the in-depth interview and focus group discussion, which were conducted via a recorded face-to-face interview.

Thematic analysis was utilized to assess the qualitative data collected through interviews and focus group discussions. This strategy enables the researcher to detect emergent patterns, themes, and meanings in participants' tales (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The data will be properly recorded and structured to guarantee that all themes are based on actual participant experiences. To increase the credibility of the findings, triangulation will be used, comparing insights from individual interviews and focus group discussions. This information cross-checking will help to ensure the study's results are accurate and consistent.

Ethical standards will be scrupulously followed during the investigation. The participants' privacy and confidentiality will be respected. Pseudonyms will replace actual names in transcripts and reports. The study will adhere to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, guaranteeing that all personal data is secured. Participants have the option to withdraw at any point without penalty. The researcher will guarantee that participation is voluntary and that the study does not cause psychological or professional harm.

Results and Discussion

This study examined teachers lived experiences in implementing the Strengthened Senior High School (SHS) Curriculum using thematic analysis. Two overarching themes emerged: **(1) Experiencing Challenges in Curriculum Implementation** and **(2) Demonstrating Teacher Adaptability and Professional Growth**, each comprising interrelated sub-themes that reflect both systemic constraints and teacher agency in curriculum reform.

Table 1. Lived Experiences in Implementing the Strengthened Senior High School

Main Theme	Sub- theme
Experiencing Challenges in Curriculum Implementation	Limited Preparation Time and Readiness
	Insufficient Instructional Materials
	Resource and School Support Limitations
Demonstrating Teacher Adaptability and Professional Growth	Adaptive and Innovative Teaching Practices
	Collaboration and Collegial Support
	Professional Commitment and Reflective Practice

Main Theme 1: Experiencing Challenges in Curriculum Implementation

The first emerging topic, Experiencing Challenges in Curriculum Implementation, captures the variety of challenges instructors encountered during the early phases of implementing the Strengthened Senior High School Curriculum. Their experiences reflect a landscape characterized by limited preparation time, poor orientation, and insufficient institutional support, all of which restricted teachers' ability to confidently and consistently execute the new curriculum requirements. Many viewed the process as "overwhelming," pointing out that aspirations for curricular congruence and pedagogical innovation frequently clashed with the reality of insufficient or delayed teaching materials, limited school resources, and no administrative support.

These structural limits set off a loop in which instructors had to interpret new competencies, restructure classes, and alter assessment procedures while also correcting for deficiencies in resources and support systems. As one teacher expressed,

“Ang pag-implement sa Strengthen SHS curriculum kay makapabug-at ug makapakaapoy. Taas kaayo ang mga ekspektasyon, apan kulang ang mga kapanguhaan. (Implementing the strengthened SHS curriculum was overwhelming. Expectations were high, but resources were limited)” - P2

Demonstrating how structural flaws directly impacted classroom practice. This topic also emphasizes the ongoing gap between curricular reform and implementation competence, mirroring global findings that educational transformation typically outpaces teacher training and school-level preparedness. Within this theme, three interconnected subcomponents emerge: (a) limited preparation time and readiness, referring to compressed timelines and insufficient training; (b) insufficient instructional materials, indicating incomplete, outdated, or delayed resources; and (c) resource and school support limitations, capturing the broader institutional constraints that shaped teachers' day-to-day curriculum delivery.

Limited Preparation Time and Readiness. Teachers often said that the given preparation time was hurried, leaving them stressed and mentally unprepared for the demands of the new curriculum. Several participants stated that they only had "a few weeks to study everything," resulting in severe stress, ambiguity, and hesitancy in providing newly specified abilities. The tight time frame hindered their capacity to examine topic standards, adapt lesson plans, and link assessments with the improved SHS curriculum. As the participant stated:

"Ang mga trainings and specialization kay naghatag sa amoa ug foundation, pero dili man siya ga-aligned sa Strengthen nga curriculum requirements. (My training and specialization gave me a foundation, but they were not always aligned with the strengthened curriculum's requirements.)" - P1

This demonstrates the teacher's realization that, while their educational background and professional training offered important knowledge and abilities, they were not totally enough to meet the demands of the newly reinforced SHS curriculum. This implies a discrepancy between teachers' current abilities and revised curricular requirements, implying that the reforms brought new topic areas, pedagogical techniques, or assessment methodologies that were not sufficiently addressed in their previous training. As a result, the instructor felt both prepared and unprepared, knowing fundamental teaching concepts but missing the specialized knowledge required to effectively convey certain courses or competences. This reflects a larger systemic challenge in which curricular improvements frequently outpace teacher preparation, necessitating more training, upskilling, and ongoing professional development for successful implementation. This is consistent with the findings of Orbeta et al. (2019), who found comparable experiences among instructors throughout the K-12 transition, in which little preparation time and unclear instructions hampered successful curriculum implementation.

From a theoretical sense, these experiences are consistent with Thorndike's Law of Readiness, which states that people accomplish activities more efficiently when they are both mentally and physically prepared. When preparedness is weakened, performance, motivation, and satisfaction suffer. In this scenario, a lack of enough preparation time undermined instructors' instructional confidence and decreased their willingness to fully participate with the new curriculum. Furthermore, the situation is consistent with Change Management Theory concepts, including Kotter's argument that change projects fail when stakeholders lack clear knowledge, readiness, and support. With curricular improvements coming before capacity-building, the system unwittingly placed teachers in a reactive role rather than establishing them as prepared implementers. Thus, the observed readiness gap is a systemic concern caused by poor planning, restricted orientation, and a lack of incremental, scaffolded support elements, all of which hindered the early implementation phase.

Insufficient Instructional Materials. Participants reported a substantial lack of textbooks, learning modules, and curriculum-aligned references, which limited their capacity to deliver courses successfully. Several teachers stated that they had to "rely on whatever online materials [they] could find," even if such resources did not entirely align with the mandated learning competencies. One participant emphasized,

"Ang mga interuactional materials kay kulang jud kaayo tapos dugay pa jud maabot ang uban kung naa man. (Instructional materials were incomplete or arrived late)" - P4

This demonstrates the teacher's dissatisfaction with the irregular and delayed delivery of crucial instructional tools. This suggests that the tools required to teach the upgraded SHS curriculum, such as textbooks, modules, and guides, were either missing crucial information or arrived well after classes had

begun. As a result, teachers lacked the resources they needed to prepare courses in advance, connect classroom activities with skills, and give organized learning assistance to students.

This problem got worse by teacher findings that pupils sometimes had more materials than the teachers, showing the uneven and unequal allocation of instructional resources among schools. Such differences left educators in a situation where they had to produce, modify, or look for alternate materials typically from online sources that did not entirely fit with curricular requirements. This technique not only increased their burden, but it also resulted in variations in instructional delivery, since the quality and usefulness of materials differed amongst teachers.

The participant's experience demonstrates how resource delays and gaps interrupt curriculum implementation, limit teaching effectiveness, and push teachers to adjust for systemic flaws through extra effort and improvisation. Capturing the irritation created by inconsistency and late delivery of critical resources. Others expressed worry that pupils sometimes received more learning materials than instructors, indicating an unequal and inequitable distribution of instructional resources among schools. This caused numerous teachers to design or find their own resources, which increased their workload and contributed to variations in educational delivery.

The paucity of materials has long been highlighted as a persistent issue in Philippine curriculum changes. Helpline PH (2025) and Bentayao et al. (2024) both stated that instructors experienced restricted, delayed, or incomplete instructional resources in the early phases of the Strengthened SHS trial, limiting their readiness. The circumstance is also consistent with Thorndike's Law of Readiness, which states that effective performance is dependent not only on psychological and professional readiness, but also on the availability of proper tools and situations. In this environment, a lack of suitable resources hampered teachers' preparation by denying them the tools they needed to properly organize, deliver, and assess learning. Furthermore, Resource Dependency Theory argues that schools rely on external entities (such as DepEd and regional offices) to offer learning resources; when these external inputs fail, instructors face restrictions that have a direct impact on instructional quality. Thus, the continual shortage of teaching resources demonstrates how structural weaknesses rather than teacher capacity frequently dictate the quality and consistency of curriculum implementation.

Resource and School Support Limitations. Participants stated that, despite attempts by school leaders to give guidance, the resources available at the school level were insufficient to satisfy the demands of the expanded curriculum. Teachers claimed that administrative support frequently lacked real instruments, such as updated modules, working laboratories, or subject-specific training, making it difficult to transform instructions into successful classroom practice. One teacher noted:

“Bisan gamay ra kaayo ug facilitoes, kay nakabuhay gihapon mi ug lesson nga magamit labaw na sa paggamit ug mga local na halimbawa. (Even with limited facilities, I was able to make lessons relevant by using local examples)” - P3

Demonstrates the teacher's ability to adjust teaching despite considerable resource restrictions. While noting the absence of proper school facilities such as updated libraries, working laboratories, or sufficient instructional tools the participant highlights their efforts to keep learning interesting and relevant to students' lives. The teacher used local examples to implement contextualized teaching, an approach that situates learning within students' cultural, community, and daily experiences. This is an example of educational resilience, in which the instructor compensates for institutional restrictions by inventiveness and contextual adaptability.

The remark is also consistent with constructivist learning theory, which holds that learners create knowledge more successfully when new concepts are embedded in familiar situations. It also mirrors the ideas of Teacher Resilience Theory, which emphasizes the ability of teachers to adapt techniques, stay goal-oriented, and maintain student engagement even in tough settings. Instead of allowing restricted facilities to impede education, the participant exhibited agency and resourcefulness, which mitigated the negative consequences of insufficient school assistance. Overall, the statement demonstrates that, despite

structural limits, teachers used locally accessible materials and real-world examples to keep training relevant and successful. Additionally, one participant shared,

“Nakadawat mig guidance sa among principal, pero ang mga resources sa library kay outdated tapos ang training materials wala man namo nadawat mao to lisod kaayo siya na magamit sa amoa. (We received guidance from our principal, but the library was outdated and the training materials were missing, so it was hard to translate advice into practice)” -P3.

As a result, teachers had to depend extensively on personal initiative and improvisation, which increased effort and impacted instructional uniformity. This demonstrates how organizational preparedness and material support, as stressed by Weiner's Organizational preparedness for Change Theory, are crucial for successful curriculum implementation. In the context of implementing the Strengthened Senior High School (SHS) Curriculum, Weiner's Organizational Readiness for Change Theory emphasizes the significance of psychological and structural readiness in schools. The theory posits that successful change depends not only on the willingness and commitment of individuals (teachers and leaders) but also on the organization's capacity to provide the necessary resources, infrastructure, and support systems (Weiner, 2009). In this study, teachers reported insufficient training, delayed instructional materials, and limited school-based resources, which constrained their ability to translate curriculum reforms into effective classroom practices. Even when school leaders offered guidance, the lack of tangible support such as updated modules, functional laboratories, or adequate teaching aids demonstrated low organizational readiness. According to Weiner's framework, these gaps reduce collective efficacy and impede the successful implementation of reforms, emphasizing that both human motivation and material capacity are critical for curriculum change to succeed.

Emphasizing both a lack of suitable infrastructure and the importance of teacher improvisation. Others expressed worries about obsolete libraries, a lack of current training resources, and insufficient school-based assistance for complicated or specialized courses. These gaps frequently required teachers to create their own resources or reuse unrelated information, resulting in inconsistent educational delivery and an increased burden. The need to "make do" with inadequate assistance stressed instructors' time while also jeopardizing the depth and precision of curricular implementation.

These experiences support UNESCO's (2022) claim that curriculum revisions are unlikely to be successful when schools lack the material and institutional underpinnings necessary for successful instruction. According to the Context–Input–Process–Output (CIPO) Model, the "process" of instructional implementation was directly compromised by the poor "input" elements, such as facilities, resources, and administrative support. Furthermore, Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory demonstrates how inadequacies in the institutional environment (exosystem and mesosystem elements) impact teachers' day-to-day classroom practices, frequently limiting their capacity to meet curricular objectives. The teachers' testimonies indicate obvious deficiencies in organizational preparation, a theme stressed in Weiner's (2009) Organizational preparation for Change Theory, which asserts that reform initiatives fail when institutions lack both the resources and collective competence to enable the change. In the instance of the trial implementation in Davao City, the lack of strong school-level support compromised the curriculum's objectives, allowing teachers to assume duties that should have been supported by institutional structures.

Main Theme 2: Demonstrating Teacher Adaptability and Professional Growth

Despite facing considerable challenges in implementing the Strengthened Senior High School (SHS) Curriculum, teachers consistently demonstrated resilience, professionalism, and a capacity for adaptation. Participants described turning limitations into opportunities for creativity and innovation. For example, one teacher shared,

“Bisan pa man sa daghang mga limitasyon, giusip ko kini nga usa ka oportunidad aron makahimo og mas makalingaw ug makapaintereres nga mga kalibokan. (While there were many limitations, I took it as an opportunity to create more engaging activities)” P3,

Reflects the teacher's proactive and positive approach to curriculum implementation problems. Despite restrictions such as limited educational materials and resources, the participant concentrated on creating courses that actively engaged students. This indicates a teacher's versatility and capacity to turn challenges into opportunities for creativity and innovation. It is also consistent with constructivist learning philosophy, which stresses providing meaningful, student-centered learning experiences. Overall, the statement emphasizes how reflective and resourceful approaches allow teachers to maintain instructional quality even in challenging contexts. Rather than being discouraged by resource gaps, they used these constraints to design interactive and contextually relevant lessons. Another participant highlighted the importance of contextualization, stating,

“Bisan pa sa limitado nga pasilidad, nakahimo gihapon ko nga mahimong mas may kalabutan ang mga leksyon pinaagi sa paggamit og mga lokal nga pananglitan. (Even with limited facilities, I was able to make lessons relevant by using local examples)” P3,

Describes how the teacher modified lessons to address resource restrictions. Despite a lack of suitable facilities or materials, the participant ensured that lectures were engaging by linking information to students' real-life experiences and local context. This represents contextualized education, in which learning is built on familiar, culturally appropriate examples to improve comprehension. It also indicates teacher resilience and adaptive skill, indicating the capacity to maintain instructional quality despite systemic constraints. Overall, the statement emphasizes the teacher's ingenuity and dedication to providing successful, student-centered learning. It also demonstrates how instructors leveraged students' life experiences and local resources to sustain relevant learning.

Collaboration also developed as an important tactic. Teachers said that collaborative problem-solving, mentorship, and peer conversations helped them deal with uncertainty in curriculum content and delivery. As one participant explained,

“Nakat-on ko nga ang kaandam dili lang mahitungod sa pagpangandam sa magtutudlo—kini usab naglakip sa kolektibong suporta, sama sa igo nga mga kapanguhaan ug padayon nga pagbansay. (I learned that readiness is not only about teacher preparation—it is also about collective support involving resources and continuous training)” P1

Emphasizes the teacher's understanding that effective curriculum implementation goes beyond individual effort. It highlights the value of teamwork, peer support, and structural assistance, such as access to resources and continual professional development. This viewpoint is consistent with Weiner's Organizational Readiness for transformation Theory, which holds that both human commitment and organizational capability are required for effective transformation. The participant's perspective demonstrates that teacher preparedness is connected with the larger school environment, emphasizing the need of communal support in maintaining instructional quality. Overall, it reveals that professional development and curricular performance are dependent on both individual effort and systemic assistance. demonstrating that professional development goes beyond individual effort and includes community and collegial assistance. Furthermore, participants underlined the value of reflective practice and a commitment to continual progress. Additionally, a teacher remarked,

“Gikan niining mga kasinatian, nasabtan ko nga ang malampusong pagpatuman nagkinahanglan og andam nga magtutudlo ug lig-on nga sistematikong suporta , Andam nga magtutudlo ug sistematikong suporta. (From these experiences, I realized that successful implementation requires both teacher readiness and systemic support, Teacher readiness and systemic support)” -P5

Reflects the teacher's understanding that effective curriculum delivery is contingent on both individual and organizational variables. It highlights that even well-prepared and dedicated teachers cannot effectively implement changes in the absence of proper resources, administrative supervision, and institutional support. This is consistent with Weiner's Organizational Readiness for Change Theory, which emphasizes the importance of motivation and ability at both the individual and organizational levels for effective change. The participant's response emphasizes the importance of teacher preparation

and institutional infrastructure in maintaining instructional quality. Overall, it demonstrates that the most effective curriculum implementation occurs when human initiative and structural support work together.

The participants' viewpoints demonstrate a dynamic interplay between individual agency, professional responsibility, and collaborative problem-solving. Despite structural restrictions, teachers demonstrated adaptive skill by relying on creativity, local knowledge, and peer support to sustain curriculum implementation. This is consistent with Constructivist Learning Theory, which stresses teachers' roles as facilitators of contextualized knowledge, and Teacher Resilience Theory, which emphasizes educators' abilities to retain professional competence under stress (Gu & Day, 2007). Collectively, these experiences are captured in the three clustered themes: Adaptive and Innovative Teaching Practices, Collaboration and Collegial Support, and Professional Commitment and Reflective Practice, demonstrating that professional growth and adaptability are critical mechanisms for successful curriculum delivery even in resource-constrained environments.

Adaptive and Innovative Teaching Practices. Teachers responded to limits by developing inventive and adaptable teaching methods that enabled them to sustain instructional quality despite systemic and material constraints. They contextualized foreign or externally developed materials, altered content to reflect local student experiences, and even created their own educational tools to cover gaps. One participant shared,

“Bisan pa sa daghang mga limitasyon, gihimo ko kini nga oportunidad aron makabuhay og mas makalingaw ug makapainterer nga mga kalibokan. (While there were many limitations, I took it as an opportunity to create more engaging activities)” -P3

Reflects on the teacher's proactive and constructive approach to curriculum implementation issues. Rather than perceiving resource limits as a barrier, the participant used them as a catalyst for creative and innovative teaching, creating sessions that actively engaged students. This exhibits teacher flexibility and problem-solving abilities, including the capacity to adjust educational tactics in response to constraints. Emphasizing that limits become a motivator for creativity rather than a deterrent. Additionally, another teacher noted,

“Bisan pa sa kakulang sa mga pasilidad, nakahimo gihapon ko nga mahimong mas may kalabutan ang mga leksyon pinaagi sa paggamit og mga lokal nga pananglitan. (Even with limited facilities, I was able to make lessons relevant by using local examples)” - P3

Highlights the teacher's ability to adapt instruction despite insufficient resources. By incorporating students' everyday experiences and local contexts, the teacher ensured that lessons remained meaningful and engaging. This demonstrates contextualized teaching, where learning is grounded in familiar, culturally relevant examples to enhance understanding. It also reflects teacher resilience and adaptive expertise, showing the capacity to maintain instructional quality under challenging conditions. Illustrating the practice of contextualized teaching, which situates learning within students' lived experiences to enhance understanding and engagement. Several participants described these experiences as opportunities to “be creative” and make lessons meaningful, showing that they actively transformed challenges into learning opportunities for students.

These findings are reinforced by Subia (2020), who discovered that Filipino instructors frequently compensate for educational system shortcomings through adaptive and inventive techniques. Thorndike's Law of Readiness proposes that teachers' intrinsic motivation and willingness to adapt are critical mechanisms for dealing with low organizational readiness; when external support is limited, teachers' internal preparedness and resourcefulness allow them to continue providing effective instruction. In this study, teacher creativity served as both a coping mechanism and a professional development process, helping educators to remain engaged, meet learning objectives, and reflect on their own practices. This demonstrates that teacher adaptation is more than just a reactive strategy; it is a purposeful, reflective approach that supports curriculum implementation under difficult situations.

Collaboration and Collegial Support. Participants stressed the significance of cooperation and collaborative approaches as they navigated the hurdles of implementing the pilot Strengthened Senior

High School (SHS) Curriculum. Teachers identified activities such as regular exchange of instructional materials, co-planning lessons, and collaborative problem-solving as critical techniques for preserving instructional quality. One participant shared,

“Sa matag bigayon nga dili ko sigurado sa usa ka leksyon, mokonsulta ko sa usa ka kauban nga nakatudlo na niini kaniadto, ug maghisgot mi og mga paagi aron mas masabtan kini sa mga estudyante. (Whenever I was unsure about a lesson, I would consult a colleague who had taught the topic before, and we would brainstorm ways to make it clearer for the students)” - P2

It demonstrates how the teacher relies on cooperation and peer help to overcome educational problems. It demonstrates how asking input and establishing methods with colleagues helps clarify content and enhance course delivery. This aligns with Social Constructivist concepts (Vygotsky, 1978), which stress learning through social engagement and information exchange. The technique also exhibits professional flexibility, as teachers employed collaborative problem-solving to handle unexpected themes while maintaining instructional quality. demonstrating how teamwork enabled them to clarify information, create more effective learning activities, and handle unfamiliar abilities. Another teacher noted that working closely with peers provided emotional and professional support, stating that without such collegial networks, the workload and stress would have been “unbearable” (P1). These collaborative efforts not only helped teachers overcome material and instructional constraints but also fostered reflective practice, knowledge exchange, and professional growth.

The significance of such collaboration is consistent with Fullan's (2016) theory of educational change, which emphasizes that reform initiatives are most successful when teachers work within a supportive professional culture that promotes shared responsibility, continuous dialogue, and collaborative problem-solving. From a theoretical standpoint, this is consistent with Social Constructivism (Vygotsky, 1978), which emphasizes the importance of social interaction and collaborative learning in gaining professional knowledge and instructional competence. Collaboration was used in this study as both a coping strategy and a catalyst for professional growth, allowing instructors to traverse systemic limits and sustain curriculum implementation despite limited resources and high demand. The findings underscore the need for schools to institutionalize collaborative structures, mentorship programs, and professional learning communities to ensure that reforms are implemented effectively and sustainably.

Professional Commitment and Reflective Practice. Despite facing considerable obstacles, teachers consistently expressed a strong dedication to ensuring that students receive high-quality instruction. Participants described engaging in long-term planning, continuously reflecting on and adapting lesson designs, and seeking out professional development opportunities to enhance their ability to implement the Strengthened SHS Curriculum effectively. One teacher reflected,

“Gikan niining mga kasinatian, nasabtan ko nga ang malampusong pagpatuman nagkinahanglan og kaandam sa magtutudlo ug lig-on nga sistematikong suporta. (From these experiences, I realized that successful implementation requires both teacher readiness and systemic support)” - P5

Reflects the teacher's recognition that effective curriculum delivery depends on both individual and organizational factors. It emphasizes that even well-prepared and committed teachers cannot fully implement reforms without adequate resources, administrative guidance, and institutional support. This aligns with Weiner's Organizational Readiness for Change Theory (2009), which highlights that successful change requires both the motivation of individuals and the structural capacity of organizations. The participant's reflection underscores the interconnectedness of teacher preparedness and systemic infrastructure in sustaining instructional quality. Overall, it illustrates that curriculum implementation is most effective when personal initiative and structural support work together.

Highlighting how reflection on practice, combined with awareness of institutional limitations, informed their ongoing instructional decisions. Teachers shared strategies such as modifying activities to fit learners' needs, contextualizing lessons with local examples, and creating supplemental resources when official materials were unavailable, demonstrating both adaptability and creativity. They emphasized that

iterative reflection on what worked and what did not allowed them to refine lessons, improve student engagement, and maintain learning continuity even in challenging conditions.

These practices align with the Department of Education's professional standards, which emphasize reflective practice, lifelong learning, and a commitment to student-centered instruction. The findings also resonate with Teacher Resilience Theory (Gu & Day, 2007), highlighting how educators' professional identity, intrinsic motivation, and adaptive strategies enable them to persevere and sustain instructional quality despite systemic constraints. Additionally, Schön's (1983) reflective practitioner model underscores how teachers analyze and learn from experience to improve practice, which was evident in participants' iterative planning and adjustments. Overall, the study suggests that teachers' reflective practice, adaptability, and professional commitment are central to sustaining curriculum implementation, transforming constraints into opportunities for growth, and ensuring that students' learning experiences remain meaningful, engaging, and aligned with curricular goals.

Conclusion, and Future Direction

The study concluded that although teachers showed strong resilience, creativity, and adaptability, their efforts were often hindered by systemic and institutional shortcomings such as limited preparation time, inadequate resources, weak infrastructure, and insufficient institutional support. These challenges placed excessive pressure on teachers to compensate for structural deficiencies, demonstrating that individual effort alone cannot sustain effective curriculum implementation. The findings highlighted the importance of both individual and organizational readiness, consistent with Weiner's Organizational Readiness for Change Theory, which emphasizes the need for both psychological and structural preparedness. While teachers were highly motivated and committed, uneven organizational readiness created a gap between curriculum expectations and classroom realities. Teacher adaptability helped mitigate some challenges, but it was not enough to replace systematic planning, adequate resources, and institutional backing. The study emphasized that sustained curriculum reform requires alignment between teacher competence and system readiness.

Overall, the research recommended a whole-system approach to curriculum reform that strengthens both teacher capacity and institutional support structures. It stressed the need for continuous professional development, high-quality instructional materials, strong leadership, clear policies, and effective monitoring systems to ensure consistent and equitable learning outcomes. The findings also underscored the importance of collaboration, infrastructure development, and responsive feedback mechanisms to support teachers in implementing curricular changes effectively. Ultimately, the study advocated for comprehensive educational frameworks that empower teachers, stabilize school systems, and promote high-quality, equitable education for all learners.

References

- Alipio, M. (2020). Education during COVID-19 era: Are learners in a less-economically developed country ready for e-learning? *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3586311>
- Alkharusi, H., Al-Sinani, M., Al-Musawi, A., Al-Hosni, K., & Al-Balushi, A. (2020). Readiness for e-learning in higher education institutions in Oman. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(3), 1747–1765. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-019-10019-0>
- Bayani, R., & Bonotan, A. (2021). Sustained professional development and its impact on teacher readiness in Mindanao schools. *International Journal of Education Research and Innovation*, 15, 145–160.
- Bentayao, G. L., Cagape, W., & Quibod, C. P. (2024, November 7). School head's management practices on policy changes in Davao City: MATATAG curriculum implementation in focus. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*. <https://eprajournals.com/IJCM/article/14224>

- Bentayao, J., Santos, R. M., & Villanueva, C. (2024). Challenges and opportunities in the early implementation of the strengthened SHS curriculum. *Philippine Journal of Education Research*, 12(1), 45–62.
- Bentayao, R. V., Agustin, M. R., & Villanueva, M. J. (2024). Teacher experiences in the pilot implementation of the strengthened senior high school curriculum. *Philippine Journal of Education and Human Development*, 12(1), 45–60.
- Carroll, C., Patterson, M., Wood, S., Booth, A., Rick, J., & Balain, S. (2007). A conceptual framework for implementation fidelity. *Implementation Science*, 2(1), 40. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-2-40>
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2017). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 21(2), 97–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2017.1398646>
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute. <https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/product/effective-teacher-professional-development-report>
- Department of Education. (2017). *Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers*. DepEd.
- Department of Education. (2025). *Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS)*. DepEd.
- El-Hamamsy, L., Monnier, E.-C., Avry, S., Chessel-Lazzarotto, F., Liégeois, G., Bruno, B., & Dehler Zufferey, J. (2023). An adapted cascade model to scale primary school digital education curricular reforms and teacher professional development programs. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2306.02751>
- Fullan, M. (2016). *The new meaning of educational change* (5th ed.). Teachers College Press.
- Gore, J., Lloyd, A., Smith, M., Bowe, J., Ellis, H., & Lubans, D. (2017). Effects of professional development on the quality of teaching: Results from a randomized controlled trial of Quality Teaching Rounds. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 68, 99–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.08.007>
- Gu, Q., & Day, C. (2007). Teachers' resilience: A necessary condition for effectiveness. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 23(8), 1302–1316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2006.06.006>
- Hall, G. E., & Hord, S. M. (2015). *Implementing change: Patterns, principles, and potholes* (4th ed.). Pearson.
- Helpline PH. (2025, June 12). Strengthened senior high school program: A promising start that left teachers hanging. *Helpline PH*. <https://helplineph.com/opinion/strengthened-senior-high-school-program-pilot/>
- Helpline PH. (2025). Teacher experiences on the strengthened SHS curriculum: Early observations and insights. *Helpline PH Research Reports*.
- Holt, D. T., Helfrich, C. D., Hall, C. G., & Weiner, B. J. (2010). Are you ready? How health professionals can comprehensively conceptualize readiness for change. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 25(1), 50–55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-009-1112-3>
- Kotter, J. P. (1996). *Leading change*. Harvard Business School Press.
- Kraft, M. A., Blazar, D., & Hogan, D. (2018). The effect of teacher coaching on instruction and achievement: A meta-analysis of the causal evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 88(4), 547–588. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654318759268>
- Llego, J. H. (2022). Challenges in the implementation of the K–12 curriculum in Philippine secondary schools. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 10(4), 85–96.
- Lucero, H. R., Victoriano, J. M., Carpio, J. T., & Fernando, P. G., Jr. (2022). Assessment of e-learning readiness of faculty members and students in Philippine higher education institutions. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2202.06069>

- Lucero, M. B., Custodio, J. E., & Agaton, C. B. (2022). E-learning readiness of faculty and students in Philippine higher education during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Education Sciences*, 12(3), 194. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12030194>
- Nguyen, T. M., & Bui, H. T. (2020). Instructional practices in Southeast Asian classrooms: Teacher delivery and curriculum reform. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 21(3), 421–436. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-020-09634-7>
- Oketch, M., Mutisya, M., Ngware, M., & Ezech, A. (2020). When provision does not guarantee learning: Textbooks and literacy in sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 77, 102237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2020.102237>
- Orbeta, A., Abrigo, M., Cabochan, M., & Francisco, K. (2019). *Process evaluation of the K–12 program implementation*. Philippine Institute for Development Studies. <https://pids.gov.ph>
- Orbeta, A., Abrigo, M., Lagarto, M., & Caliso, R. (2019). *Senior high school and the labor market: Perspectives of Grade 12 students and human resource officers* (Discussion Paper No. 2019-13). Philippine Institute for Development Studies.
- Pei, C., & Lu, L. H. (2024). Improving teachers' readiness for change through sociotechnical organization development interventions. *ABAC ODI Journal: Vision. Action. Outcome*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.14456/abacodijournal.2024.9>
- Pei, X., & Lu, Y. (2024). Enhancing teacher readiness for curriculum reform through performance feedback. *Frontiers in Education*, 9, 1356221. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2024.1356221>
- Prinsloo, M., & Krause, L. (2021). Curriculum reform and contextualized instructional materials in African schools. *Prospects*, 50(3), 323–339. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-020-09519-7>
- Salandanan, G. (2019). Textbook shortages and teacher improvisation in Philippine public schools. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 2(1), 56–65. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v2i1.114>
- Schön, D. A. (1983). *The reflective practitioner: How professionals think in action*. Basic Books.
- Subia, G. S. (2020). Filipino teachers' creativity and innovation in times of adversity. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 9(4), 67–76.
- SunStar Davao. (2025, April 26). DepEd-Davao: New SHS curriculum still experimental. *SunStar*.
- Thorndike, E. L. (1932). *The fundamentals of learning*. Teachers College, Columbia University.
- UNESCO. (2022). *Reimagining curriculum reform for the 21st century: Global challenges and opportunities*. UNESCO Publishing.
- UNESCO. (2022). *Reimagining our futures together: A new social contract for education*. UNESCO Publishing.
- Vakola, M. (2016). The reasons behind change resistance in the workplace. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 29(1), 45–62. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOCM-05-2015-0089>
- Villaneza, R. (2019, August 1). Scaling education programs in the Philippines: A policymaker's perspective. *Brookings Institution*.
- Volf, K., Vranješević, J., & Pavlović, J. (2021). Fidelity of curriculum implementation. *European Journal of Education*, 56(4), 651–666. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12482>
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- Weiner, B. J. (2009). A theory of organizational readiness for change. *Implementation Science*, 4, 67. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-4-67>

